

ON THE QUESTION OF THE SUBSTANTIATION OF THE TERM "MAILITARY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE"

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Abstract: The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in military affairs, required by the political and military leadership of the Russian Federation, must have appropriate regulatory and technical regulation. At the same time, at the government level, there is a lack of an unambiguous understanding of the terms "artificial intelligence", "robot", etc., which creates a terminological problem in the formation of regulation, and therefore the possibility of different terminological definitions in different areas of AI application is allowed. Such an opportunity is also necessary in the field of military application of AI, and, accordingly, the justification of the term "military AI" is an urgent task. The definition of "AI" given in the "National Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence for the period up to 2030" is not clear enough, so the purpose of the article is to overcome the shortcomings of this definition and develop clearer and clearer definitions of the terms "AI" and "military AI" . Method for solving the problem: first of all, the paradigm of deriving the meaning of the term "AI" from a meaningful understanding of human intelligence (HI) was adopted, and in this paradigm a three-stage scheme for solving the research problem was drawn up and implemented: first, the term "HI" is defined, then the term "AI" is defined on its basis. AI, then in the context of the derived understanding of "AI", the term "military AI" is defined. The result of solving the problem: new definitions of the terms "HI", "AI",

“military AI” have been developed, the novelty of which is given by the involvement of the necessary information about human intelligence from sources of professional knowledge in medicine and psychology. The practical significance of the solution lies in the possibility of using the developed definitions of the terms "MI", "AI", "military AI" in the regulatory and technical regulation of the field of AI and the industry of military use of AI. Key words: human intelligence, artificial intelligence, military artificial intelligence.

Definition of the term "human intelligence"

The author of this article could not find on the Internet sufficiently authoritative Russian-language sources with definitions of the term "cognitive functions". In English-language Internet resources, the term "cognitive functions" is defined differently and without any logical rigor, but in general, the opinions of the authors agree to consider it a synonym for the terms "intellectual functions", "mental processes". The Electronic Dictionary of Psychology [2], compiled by the American Psychological Association, gives the following definitions: “cognition – all forms of knowing and awareness, such as perceiving, conceiving, remembering, reasoning, judging, imagining, and problem solving. along with affect and conation, it is one of the three traditionally identified components of mind; an individual percept, idea, memory, or the like” (cognition is all forms of knowledge and awareness, such as perception, representation, memorization, reasoning, judgment, imagination, and problem solving. Along with affect and pretense, this is one of the three traditionally defined components mind, as well as individual perception, idea, memory, etc.); "cognitive functioning - the performance of the mental processes of perception, learning, memory, understanding, awareness, reasoning, judgment, intuition, and language" (cognitive functioning - the performance of the mental processes of perception, learning, memory, understanding, awareness, reasoning, judgment, intuition and language); “intellect – the intellectual functions of the mind considered

collectively; an individual's capacity for abstract, objective reasoning, especially as contrasted with his or her capacity for feeling, imagining, or acting" feel, imagine or act); □ “intellectual function – any of the mental functions involved in acquiring, developing, and relating ideas, concepts, and hypotheses. Memory, imagination, and judgment can also be considered intellectual functions ”(an intellectual function is any of the mental functions involved in the acquisition, development and linking of ideas, concepts and hypotheses. Memory, imagination and judgment can also be considered intellectual functions). The Russian logical dictionary [2] contains the following definitions: - “cognitive – knowable, corresponding to knowledge”; □“intellect is an integral set of functions, manifestations of the activity of highly organized matter — the human brain (thinking, emotions, will, fantasies, etc.), aimed at understanding and transforming nature, society and oneself”; “artificial intelligence is a machine that performs activities that would normally require a human brain.” The Russian Internet resource "Dictionaries Online" [1], which contains a large number of dictionaries and encyclopedias (including psychological ones), gives many definitions of terms related to cognition and intelligence - here are just a few of them: - "cognitive processes - cognitive processes of a person, including his sensations, perception, attention, imagination, memory, thinking, speech”; “intelligence is a relatively stable structure of the mental abilities of an individual, manifested in various areas of practical and theoretical activity”; “intelligence is a general ability to learn and solve problems, which determines the success of any activity and underlies other abilities; the system of all cognitive (cognitive) abilities of an individual: sensation, perception, memory, representation, thinking, imagination; the ability to solve problems without trial and error "in the mind"; - "mind, mind - the ability to think and understand"; - “thinking is the highest form of cognitive activity, which determines the internal connections between people, objects and phenomena, is closely related to memory, speech, the ability to analyze and synthesize, generalize previously accumulated knowledge and newly

acquired information. A person's thinking is judged by his statements and activities. The level of thinking and the ability to penetrate into the essence of emerging problems, to develop the most adequate solutions are included in the concept of intelligence.

The CogniFit company, one of the leading companies developing computer programs for assessing and training the intellectual abilities of people, reports its understanding of the terms under consideration [2]: - “Cognitiveness is the ability to perceive and process data that comes to us in various ways (perception, experience, beliefs...) to turn them into knowledge. This ability covers various cognitive processes, such as learning, attention, memory, speech, reasoning, decision making, etc., which are part of intellectual development and experience”; - “Cognitive functions are mental processes that allow us to receive, select, accumulate, process, create and restore information. It helps us understand the world around us and communicate with it.”From the above examples, the following conclusions can be drawn: - in foreign sources, cognition is understood in most cases as a synonym for intelligence and is repeated more often than intelligence, while in domestic sources cognition is most often understood more narrowly in the aspect of cognition and can be considered in further as part of intellectuality and applied when it is necessary to emphasize the cognitive aspect of intellectuality; in the definitions of intellectuality, the terms “function”, “process”, “ability” are used (one by one and together), which does not give clarity to the definitions; - in order to achieve clarity and clarity of definitions, it is necessary to involve the philosophical categories "essence and phenomenon" and to assume that the intellectual functions and processes of the human brain are manifestations of his intellectual abilities, which together constitute the intellectual essence of a person. In accordance with these findings, it is proposed to define the IH: human intelligence is a stable complex of human mental abilities, which are formed by training and personal experience, are manifested and consciously used by a person in meaningful behavior, including planning,

organizing and conducting purposeful activities, as well as in cognition. This definition in itself does not yet give complete clarity of understanding of the IH, because it contains the expression “mental abilities of a person”, which has not yet been defined. To clarify the issue of human intelligence, it is best to turn to knowledge from the field in which specialists work with the intelligence of people professionally and responsibly. The authoritative written source of expertise on human intelligence is the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, the latest 5th edition of which, DSM-5, was developed and published by the American Psychiatric association in 2013 According to the DSM-5, the general mental abilities of an adult: - firstly, are associated with the intellectual functions (refers to intellectual functions) of a person, to which the DSM-5 includes: reasoning, problem solving, planning, abstract thinking, judgment, learning from instruction and experience, and practical understanding (reasoning, problem solving, planning, abstract thinking, judgment, learning from instruction and experience, and practical understanding). The critical components of human intellectual functions are: verbal comprehension, working memory, perceptual reasoning, quantitative reasoning, abstract thought, and cognitive efficacy; secondly, they are manifested in everyday adaptive functioning of a person, which is provided by memory, language, reading, writing, mathematical reasoning, acquiring practical knowledge, solving problems, judgments in new situations; awareness of the thoughts, feelings and experiences of others; empathy, interpersonal skills, friendship ability, social judgment, learning and self-management in life conditions, including personal care, job responsibilities, money management, recreation, self-management of behavior, organization of school and work tasks (memory, language, reading, writing, math reasoning, acquisition of practical knowledge, problem solving, and judgment in novel situations, awareness of others’ thoughts, feelings, and experiences, empathy, interpersonal communication skills, friendship abilities, social judgment, learning and self-management across life settings, including personal care, job

responsibilities, money management, recreation, self-management of behavior, and school and work task organization). Simultaneous use in DSM-5 of two undifferentiated terms "mental abilities" (mental abilities) and "intellectual functions" to explain the same subject - intellectual disability - makes it difficult to understand this as well. subject, and these two terms. Therefore, a practically useful way out of this situation can be the following logical formula: - a person has mental abilities, which manifest themselves in the form of performed intellectual functions and solved intellectual tasks in volitional acts of application and realization of these abilities; □ the same names are allowed for the mental abilities of a person and their corresponding intellectual functions. Taking into account this formula, based on the recommendations of "DSM-5" and supplementing them with information from other (mentioned above) sources, it is possible to compile an extended list of human mental abilities that manifest themselves in the form of intellectual functions of the same name in human volitional acts: - selective and sustained attention; perception, recognition, memorization of objects, phenomena, events; memorization of information and personal experience; analysis and generalization of information, construction of abstractions and classifications; - orientation in space and time; - language acquisition; oral speech, writing, interpersonal communications; acceptance of learning based on instruction and experience; establishment of causal relationships; judgments and conclusions, hypotheses and proof; natural account, calculation of quantities and quantities; - forecasting; - development of meanings; - assimilation, accumulation and production of knowledge; - mobilization of the will; - setting goals and purposeful behavior; - planning of own actions; development, adoption and implementation of behavioral decisions; understanding, analysis and problem solving; awareness and overcoming of dangers, including risk assessment; - creativity; □ understanding of the actions of people around; - social adaptation. This list of mental abilities / intellectual functions of a person does not pretend to be more accurate and complete;

philosophers and psychologists should work on their professional analysis. For example, the leading Russian scientist (philosopher and mathematician) in the field of AI Finn V.K.formulated the following thirteen basic intellectual abilities of the “ideal intellect” [2]: highlighting the essential in data, goal setting and achieving planned expedient actions, finding the necessary knowledge, reasoning, making rational decisions, reflection, interest in knowledge, explanation of causes and effects, heuristic problem solving , learning and use of memory, rationalization of ideas and formation of concepts, systematization of knowledge and construction of rational theories, correction of theories according to new knowledge.

Definition of the term "military artificial intelligence"

In the context of the general understanding and definition of the term “AI” formulated above, the task of defining the term “military AI” is solved simply: military artificial intelligence, military artificial intelligence is artificial intelligence built into military equipment. At the same time, military equipment can be understood and classified, for example, as recommended in GOST [1]. Such an unexpectedly short definition of "military AI" is due to the previous meaningfully detailed general definitions of the terms "MI" and "AI", which dictates the need to include them in the future standard of military AI terms and definitions. At the same time, on the basis of the general definition of "AI" compiled above, it is possible to additionally draw up the following detailed definition of "military AI": military artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence for military purposes - various sets of mathematical methods, models and algorithms, information technology and technical design solutions that they model with varying degrees of similarity the mental abilities of a person, are built into military equipment and perform functions similar to the intellectual functions of a person. It is quite obvious that the normative classification of military AI should and will differ from the general classification of AI compiled in GOST [3]. The

development of a normative classification of military AI is a separate large task that is beyond the scope of this article and should be addressed in a separate research work. Nevertheless, for further discussion of options for classifying military AI, the following matrix classification scheme for military AI is proposed, formed by the Cartesian product of two groups of classification features, the first of which is the technical types of VT, the second is the profiles of the purpose of VT: 1) classification of military AI by technical types of VT : AI embedded in automated control systems (ACS) for military purposes (VN); AI embedded in information systems (IS), information and settlement systems (IRS), in software and hardware systems (HSS) VN; AI embedded in robotic complexes and systems (RTK and RTS) VN; AI embedded in other models, complexes and systems of military equipment that are neither ACS VN, nor IS, IRS and PAK VN, nor RTK and RTS VN; 2) classification of military AI according to the purpose profiles of BT: AI embedded in weapons⁵; AI, built into the equipment of the types of support for combat operations, which is not a weapon; AI built into the technology of information confrontation; AI embedded in the technique of testing grounds; AI embedded in training equipment; AI embedded in IS, IRS, PAC of military education; AI embedded in IS, IRS, PAK of military science. Thus, at the top hierarchical level, 28 military AI classification groups are obtained. This classification matrix can be converted into an N-dimensional one by adding other groups of classification features, for example, sets of AI characteristics from GOST [3] – control loop functions, specializations, knowledge models, information processing methods, etc., or, for example, by adding the “periodic system of AI technologies” proposed in the book [2] and shown in Fig. 1. For practical implementations of military AI from certain classification groups, corresponding groups of specifications of tactical and technical requirements for AI will be required. It should also be noted that the development of methods for the rational choice of AI types suitable for integration into a particular military equipment will soon become an urgent

scientific problem that will need to be solved. Part of the solution to this problem will be the definition of key principles for choosing AI. Now it is difficult to accurately predict these principles, but one principle can already be proposed right now - this is the principle of acceptable risk: any AI is allowed to be built into the AT if the estimated risk of failure to perform military tasks using AT with AI in case of erroneous functioning of the AI does not exceed the specified acceptable level , and the consequences of erroneous functioning of AI can be compensated by a person with an acceptable cost of resources and time.

Conclusion

As part of the urgent need to build a system of normative and technical regulation of the field of military use of AI, as well as due to insufficient clarity and clarity of the definition of the term "AI" given in the "National Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence for the period up to 2030", an urgent research task of developing new more meaningful and understandable definitions of the terms "AI" and "military AI". The problem is solved in the paradigm adopted by the author of the article for deriving the meaning of the term "AI" from a meaningful understanding of human intelligence as follows: first, the term "HI" is defined with the involvement of the necessary information from sources of professional knowledge in medicine and psychology, then, on its basis, the term "AI" is defined with the inheritance of generally recognized essential characteristics of AI, then in the context of a meaningful understanding of AI, the term "military AI" is defined as AI built into military equipment. For further semantic development of the field of military AI, a matrix scheme for its classification by two qualitative categories of military equipment (in which AI is embedded) is proposed: "by technical types of military equipment" × "by profiles of the purpose of military AI", which gives 28 classification groups of military AI at the upper hierarchical level . The results of the research carried out in the article

can be used in the development of normative and technical documents regulating the general field of AI and the field of military application of AI.

References

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